

APPENDIX A: DETAILED RESULTS OF 3FM, 4FM, AND 5FM

Table 4A: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of North America (3FM)

Models	<i>Rm-Rf</i>	SMB	HML
Fama and French	0.71	0.69	0.81
PCA	0.54	0.44	0.49
IPCA	0.62	0.52	1.74
CA	0.73	0.88	1.49

Table 4B: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of North America (4FM)

Models	<i>Rm-Rf</i>	SMB	HML	MOM
Fama and French	0.71	0.69	0.81	0.93
PCA	0.54	0.44	0.49	0.61
IPCA	0.62	0.52	1.74	2.12
CA	0.73	0.88	1.49	2.34

Table 4C: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of North America (5FM)

Models	<i>Rm-Rf</i>	SMB	HML	RMW_O	CMA
Fama and French	0.71	0.69	0.81	0.93	0.95
PCA	0.54	0.44	0.49	0.61	0.71
IPCA	0.62	0.52	1.74	2.12	2.87
CA	0.73	0.88	1.49	2.34	2.75

Table 5A: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Europe (3FM)

Models	<i>Rm-Rf</i>	SMB	HML
Fama and French	0.28	0.09	0.13
PCA	0.20	0.18	1.26
IPCA	0.23	0.32	1.38
CA	0.31	0.38	2.09

Table 5B: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Europe (4FM)

Models	<i>Rm-Rf</i>	SMB	HML	MOM
Fama and French	0.28	0.09	0.13	-0.08
PCA	0.20	0.18	1.26	2.15
IPCA	0.23	0.32	1.38	1.92
CA	0.31	0.38	2.09	2.55

Table 5C: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Europe (5FM)

Models	<i>Rm-Rf</i>	SMB	HML	RMW_O	CMA
---------------	---------------------	------------	------------	--------------	------------

Fama and French	0.28	0.09	0.13	-0.08	-0.13
PCA	0.20	0.18	1.26	2.15	2.49
IPCA	0.23	0.32	1.38	1.92	2.27
CA	0.31	0.38	2.09	2.55	2.75

Table 6A: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Japan (3FM)

Models	$Rm-Rf$	SMB	HML
Fama and French	-0.081	-1.120	-0.690
PCA	0.120	-0.180	0.044
IPCA	-0.150	-0.070	0.590
CA	-0.110	-0.080	0.430

Table 6B: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Japan (4FM)

Models	$Rm-Rf$	SMB	HML	MOM
Fama and French	-0.081	-1.120	-0.690	-0.370
PCA	0.120	-0.180	0.044	0.160
IPCA	-0.150	-0.070	0.590	0.820
CA	-0.110	-0.080	0.430	0.920

Table 6D: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Japan (5FM)

Models	$Rm-Rf$	SMB	HML	RMW_O	CMA
Fama and French	-0.081	-1.120	-0.690	-0.370	0.360
PCA	0.120	-0.180	0.044	0.160	0.260
IPCA	-0.150	-0.070	0.590	0.820	1.190
CA	-0.110	-0.080	0.430	0.920	0.960

Table 7A: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Asia (3FM)

Models	$Rm-Rf$	SMB	HML
Fama and French	0.42	0.48	1.47
PCA	0.57	0.94	2.18
IPCA	0.55	0.75	2.55
CA	0.53	0.72	2.90

Table 7B: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Asia (4FM)

Models	$Rm-Rf$	SMB	HML	MOM
Fama and French	0.42	0.48	1.47	1.77
PCA	0.57	0.94	2.18	2.81
IPCA	0.55	0.75	2.55	3.24
CA	0.53	0.72	2.90	3.71

Table 7C: Out of the sample portfolio, a sharp ratio comparison of Asia (5FM)

Models	$Rm-Rf$	SMB	HML	RMW_O	CMA
Fama and French	0.42	0.48	1.47	1.77	1.98
PCA	0.57	0.94	2.18	2.81	2.67
IPCA	0.55	0.75	2.55	3.24	3.81
CA	0.53	0.72	2.90	3.71	4.01

Table 8A: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{predicted}$ in percentage comparison of North America (3FM)

Models	R^2 Total $Rm-Rf$	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Predicted. $Rm-Rf$	R^2 Predicted. SMB	R^2 Predicted. HML
3FM	49.4%	58.4%	63.2%	64.3%	68.2%	88.2%
PCA	50.1%	42.0%	52.3%	0.1%	0.2%	0.4%
IPCA	60.2%	68.2%	74.6%	48.6%	52.4%	86.7%
CA	55.5%	62.4%	68.8%	42.2%	45.8%	68.9%

Table 8B: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{predicted}$ in percentage comparison of North America (4FM)

Models	R^2 Total $Rm-Rf$	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Total MOM	R^2 Predicted $Rm-Rf$	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML	R^2 Predicted MOM
4FM	49.4%	58.4%	63.2%	69.8%	64.3%	68.2%	88.2%	58.5%
PCA	50.1%	42.0%	52.3%	54.5%	0.1%	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%
IPCA	60.2%	68.2%	74.6%	76.7%	48.6%	52.4%	86.7%	75.3%
CA	55.5%	62.4%	68.8%	70.3%	42.2%	45.8%	68.9%	58.3%

Table 8C: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of North America (5FM)

Models	R^2 Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Total RMW_O	R^2 Total CMA	R^2 Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML	R^2 Predicted RMW_O	R^2 Predicted CMA
5FM	49.4%	58.4%	63.2%	69.8%	72.5%	64.3%	68.2%	88.2%	58.5%	69.3%
PCA	50.1%	42.0%	52.3%	54.5%	51.3%	0.1%	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%	0.3%
IPCA	60.2%	68.2%	74.6%	76.7%	79.1%	48.6%	52.4%	86.7%	75.3%	74.9%
CA	55.5%	62.4%	68.8%	70.3%	70.9%	42.2%	45.8%	68.9%	58.3%	53.3%

Table 9A: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of Europe (3FM)

Models	R^2 Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML
3FM	17.60%	30.30%	36.80%	2.06%	2.57%	2.89%
PCA	3.50%	4.70%	5.50%	0.10%	0.10%	0.30%
IPCA	16.60%	27.60%	34.60%	2.21%	2.92%	3.33%
CA	17.70%	25.60%	36.80%	2.10%	2.85%	3.21%

Table 9B: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of Europe (4FM)

Models	R^2 Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Total MOM	R^2 Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML	R^2 Predicted MOM
4FM	17.6%	30.3%	36.8%	37.7%	2.06%	2.57%	2.89%	2.86%
PCA	3.5%	4.7%	5.5%	6.3%	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%
IPCA	16.6%	27.6%	34.6%	43.2%	2.21%	2.92%	3.33%	3.23%
CA	17.7%	25.6%	36.8%	29.5%	2.10%	2.85%	3.21%	2.2%

Table 9C: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of Europe (5FM)

Models	R ² Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Total SMB	R ² Total HML	R ² Total RMW_O	R ² Total CMA	R ² Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Predicted SMB	R ² Predicted HML	R ² Predicted RMW_O	R ² Predicted CMA
5FM	17.6%	30.3%	36.8%	37.7%	36.3%	2.06%	2.57%	2.89%	2.86%	2.58%
PCA	3.5%	4.7%	5.5%	6.3%	7.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.2%
IPCA	16.6%	27.6%	34.6%	43.2%	43.0%	2.21%	2.92%	3.33%	3.23%	3.21%
CA	17.7%	25.6%	36.8%	29.5%	36.3%	2.10%	2.85%	3.21%	2.2%	2.23%

Table 10A: Out-of-sample R²_{total} and R²_{predicted} in percentage comparison of Japan (3FM)

Models	R ² Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Total SMB	R ² Total HML	R ² Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Predicted SMB	R ² Predicted HML
3FM	11.00%	11.40%	11.90%	1.50%	1.90%	1.50%
PCA	3.40%	5.10%	6.00%	0.84%	0.82%	0.81%
IPCA	15.60%	22.40%	29.30%	8.00%	7.60%	7.70%
CA	16.10%	15.80%	13.90%	1.95%	2.24%	2.73%

Table 10B: Out-of-sample R²_{total} and R²_{predicted} in percentage comparison of Japan (4FM)

Models	R ² Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Total SMB	R ² Total HML	R ² Total MOM	R ² Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Predicted SMB	R ² Predicted HML	R ² Predicted MOM
4FM	11.00%	11.40%	11.90%	12.50%	1.50%	1.90%	1.50%	1.20%
PCA	3.40%	5.10%	6.00%	6.90%	0.84%	0.82%	0.81%	0.80%
IPCA	15.60%	22.40%	29.30%	32.50%	8.00%	7.60%	7.70%	7.60%
CA	16.10%	15.80%	13.90%	14.00%	1.95%	2.24%	2.73%	2.80%

Table 10C: Out-of-sample R²_{total} and R²_{predicted} in percentage comparison of Japan (5FM)

Models	R ² Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Total SMB	R ² Total HML	R ² Total RMW_O	R ² Total CMA	R ² Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R ² Predicted SMB	R ² Predicted HML	R ² Predicted RMW_O	R ² Predicted CMA
5FM	11.00%	11.40%	11.90%	12.50%	13.10%	1.50%	1.90%	1.50%	1.20%	1.00%

PCA	3.40%	5.10%	6.00%	6.90%	7.50%	0.84%	0.82%	0.81%	0.80%	0.79%
IPCA	15.60%	22.40%	29.30%	32.50%	29.50%	8.00%	7.60%	7.70%	7.60%	7.20%
CA	16.10%	15.80%	13.90%	14.00%	12.70%	1.95%	2.24%	2.73%	2.80%	2.69%

Table 11A: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of Asia (3FM)

Models	R^2 Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML
3FM	13.70%	13.60%	28.00%	12.80%	18.10%	15.70%
PCA	2.42%	2.38%	1.28%	0.30%	0.11%	0.91%
IPCA	20.20%	9.40%	13.90%	15.00%	7.30%	13.70%
CA	23.00%	21.10%	13.40%	12.10%	12.80%	13.10%

Table 11B: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of Asia (4FM)

Models	R^2 Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Total MOM	R^2 Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML	R^2 Predicted MOM
4FM	13.70%	13.60%	28.00%	29.00%	12.80%	18.10%	15.70%	11.80%
PCA	2.42%	2.38%	1.28%	1.26%	0.30%	0.11%	0.91%	0.13%
IPCA	20.20%	9.40%	13.90%	32.60%	15.00%	7.30%	13.70%	15.90%
CA	23.00%	21.10%	13.40%	18.70%	12.10%	12.80%	13.10%	14.10%

Table 11C: Out-of-sample R^2_{total} and $R^2_{\text{predicted}}$ in percentage comparison of Asia (5FM)

Models	R^2 Total <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Total SMB	R^2 Total HML	R^2 Total RMW_O	R^2 Total CMA	R^2 Predicted <i>Rm-Rf</i>	R^2 Predicted SMB	R^2 Predicted HML	R^2 Predicted RMW_O	R^2 Predicted CMA
5FM	13.70%	13.60%	28.00%	29.00%	32.30%	12.80%	18.10%	15.70%	11.80%	13.00%
PCA	2.42%	2.38%	1.28%	1.26%	1.29%	0.30%	0.11%	0.91%	0.13%	0.14%
IPCA	20.20%	9.40%	13.90%	32.60%	41.60%	15.00%	7.30%	13.70%	15.90%	17.30%
CA	23.00%	21.10%	13.40%	18.70%	21.00%	12.10%	12.80%	13.10%	14.10%	14.30%